

Work Life Balance Issues in Indian Men- Do These Exist? A Study among Southern Railway Men

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Abstract

Work life balance has been considered an issue pertaining to working women. The challenges they face in striking a balance with work and life is a subject of considerable research. What however, is not well studied is work-life balance of men. This study seeks to add to that meagre body of literature. Analysis of data collected in this study covering 41 men shows that these men also face work life balance issues. Long working hours and demands of the job hinder work-life balance. Taking vacations, working from home, job sharing, flexi hours and flexi starting hours would help attain work life balance.

Keywords: Working men, Work life balance, Stress, flexi time, job sharing.

Introduction

Work life balance is, very simply put, "the division of one's time and focus between working and family or leisure activities"(Google dictionary) . When we talk of work life balance, a picture of a working woman with a husband, children, aging elders, a home to run, food to cook, washing and assorted chores to be done, springs to our mind; of a woman who seems to get to sit down and relax only when she boards a bus or an 'auto' or a train, to commute to work. Work-life balance issues are without any doubt issues faced primarily by working women and there can never be too much literature addressing this important area of women. Work life discussion is for women.

However, we seldom come across literature about work-life balance issues of men. Do men also face these issues? Dual career couples is now the norm and with many more men having wives who do paid work outside of homes, how do they cope? Do they help out with house work? How much time do they spend at their work places? What are their leisure activities? Until recently, the primary focus of work life balance studies has been only women. Lately however, the question of work life balance as issue, concerning men also has started taking shape. Now there is a focus on men too. It is beginning to be recognized that men also face work life balance issues.

(Gorman-Murray 2013, Emslie and Hunt 2009, Evans, Carney and Wilkinson, 2013, Lyness, Judiesch, Michael 2014, Vandello et al 2013). The work force has changed considerably in the past four decades. More and more women have joined the labour force. Even though they continue to perform their traditional duties of child rearing, take on the growing burden of elder care and home making and even with the fact that a 9 to 5 job, commute time, the time spent away from home puts them under a great deal of stress, the question that arises is, do men participate in house work to relieve women of some of the double burden they carry? These instances beg a research into the aspects of work life balance issues of men. In casual conversations in social settings, when talking about home and house work, men reveal that they chip in considerably in-home activities. Is this true?

As more and more emphasis is placed on education and society becomes more egalitarian, men's participation in child care, elder care and household chores is bound to increase even in conservative patriarchal societies such as ours, as men get involved in areas of work considered traditionally women's. There is a huge difference in the way girl children are being brought up in middle class conservative South Indian homes nowadays as compared to the early decades. Girl children go to schools and colleges are encouraged to consider various careers and given a great deal of freedom and confidence. National statistics show that enrolment of girls in high schools and colleges have increased from% to% of the total enrolment. Consequently, girls no longer grow up to be a traditional obedient docile women. In this scenario a girl on getting married, expects to be an equal partner in marriage. Her expectations from her husband is as not just husband, is not just of protection and provision, but as equal, participating father, companion and friend. Women demand a more active role from men at home. On their part, men are also changing, with the young men wanting to be part of their children's growing up process, take vacations and have family time together. The old prototype of a working male who works long hard hours, misses meals with families, skips social events so that he can rise to the top of the career ladder if need be at the expense of all. In short Professional persona is their primary identity. All this is changing rapidly. Society is changing and along with it, the traditional roles are getting overlapped. From this comes the importance of this study. Since these are matters we are seem to "know" but there is no adequate literature to support a beginning is made through this study.

Literature Review

Emslie & Hunt (2009) find that gender is firmly a part of men and women and the way they negotiate life home and work life. Work life balance is perceived as a personal issue to be dealt with by individual categories and not as a structural problem caused by lack of flexibility in the workplace and a lack of affordable child care and elder care.

Evans et al (2013) state that work life balance is also a significant and critical issue for men and that there is a paucity of research exploring work life balance among men. Men also experience conflict in finding a balance between work and family commitments in double income families. The increased responsibilities of the household fall on both women and men.

Lyness & Judiesch (2014) in a cross-country study find, based on self-reports and supervisor's appraisals that gender egalitarian values influenced the supervisors perceptions of employees work life balance.

Lunan, et al (2014) have found that employees reporting a poor work life balance reported more health problems and that it is similar for both men and women. Family policies such as child care services, extended and flexible parental leave schemes and generous support to single parents may increase reconciliation between work & domestic life as do flexible work arrangements in terms of working hours. Employees have to find their own solutions to combine work and family life.

Need of the Study

The lack of adequate literature on the subject is one of the major needs for this study, specifically as there are no studies covering working men in the Indian Railways which employs 1.3 million people, of which over 90% are men (Indian Railway statistics). We need to add to the body of literature on these issues pertaining to Indian men being more relevant to our society. This study seeks to shed some light on work-life balance from a male perspective. We need to know if men do find challenges in work life balance. If yes, how these can be tackled. This research contributes uniquely to the literature of work life balance issues among a particular group of employed Indian men, viz. Railwaymen working in South India.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to find out:

- If men have work-life balance issues.
- If they participated in house work, child and elder care.
- The causes affecting the achievement of work life balance.
- The solutions that would help in achievement of work life balance

Methodology

The Personnel department (the Human Resources Management Department) of Southern Railway, organised a week long program on soft skills Development for its senior supervisors and equivalent grade officials at Ketti in Tamil Nadu in February 2017. This researcher was invited to speak to the group about work life balance. The S.Rly. covers the geographical areas of Tamil Nadu, Kerala, the UT of Pondicherry, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Laskshwadeep Islands.

43 officials, all men, attended the program. With the consent of the organisers, a questionnaire comprising 30 questions sourced from the internet including demographic details was given to the participants. Names of the respondents were not required to be given. The questions were multiple choices as well as open ended. The respondents were asked to select as many of the choices as applicable to them in some questions. In others they had to choose only the appropriate response. They were requested to write freely their views in the open-ended questions. 41 participants responded to the questionnaire.

Data collected were organised in excel sheets. Descriptive statistics tools such as frequency and averages were employed in analysing the data obtained from the questionnaire.

Analysis of Data

Table 1 shows the demographic description of the respondents. The respondents were mostly in the age group of 31 to 59. Only 3 respondents were in the age group of 21-29 of which 2 were unmarried. 13 respondents' wives were working women while the majority (26/41) had homemakers for wives.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution Of Participants

Age Profile	Employed	Home Makers	Unmarried
21-29 yrs		1	2
31-39 yrs	2	4	
41-49 yrs	6	5	
51-59 yrs	5	16	
Total	13	26	2

Time spent on working hours, commute time to and from office and average number of hours for sleeping were added up. (The self estimated time of around 2 hours toward helping an household chores is arrived at).

Of the 37 men who responded to the question on whether they were able to balance work and life, 32 said that they were able to balance work life. 6 men constituting 16% for this question, said they were not able to balance work-life.

Table 2: Ability to balance work Life (12)

36 men responded to the question on whether they missed out on quality time with family. Out of this 27 stated they missed out a quality time.

Table 3: Miss out quality time with family or friends due to work pressure

Questions on measures that would help balance work life reveal that 14 out of 33 of those that responded to the question felt taking vacations and holidays would help, 19 out of 33 felt that job related measures such as work-from-home, job sharing, flexi start and finish times and flexi times would help attain work life balance. To a question on support systems to balance work life.

Table 4: Help balance work life

25 out of 33 looked to support from family and colleagues for work life balance. 20 out of the 41 respondents picked peers as help in the achievement of work life balance. No man responded that bringing children to office occasionally helped in achieving work life balance event.

Table 5: Help Balance Work and Family commitments

From the above analysis it is seen that

- the respondents are participating in household chores self-estimated at about two hours a day.
- a large percent of men was able to balance work life. However, the 16% of the men who said ‘No’ to ability to balance work life constitute a significant percentage.
- 75% of the respondents admitted to missing out on quality time with family due to work pressure.
- 42% and 58% of them identified vacations/time off and job sharing/flexi time as measures to help work life balance respectively.
- Over 90% of them identified support from family, colleagues, working from home or availability of laptops/mobiles as helping balance work and family commitments.
- Not a single man said bringing children to office on occasion would help balance work family commitments.

Of the twenty-eight responses to an open-ended question about WLB, twelve respondents said that WLB leads to better work and organisation would grow.

The respondents also variously stated that achieving work life balance would mean “purpose of life will be met successfully” and one need not “start living after retirement”. Better life would mean “we will be good at work”. One respondent said “work and life are parallel and should never cross each other. If circumstances required to cross, stop one thing and give precedence to other but never allow to crash”. This can be taken to mean that situational based priorities should be given. Another respondent stated that work and life are equally important for a man’s success.

Findings of the Study

The study finds that

- work life balance is an issue for men also.
- Whether wives are working in the labour market or home makers, men are increasingly involved in household chores.
- They identify family and peer support systems as enablers for achieving work life balance.

- Taking time off and family vacations along with working from home, flexi time, job sharing are measures that would enable achievement of work life balance.

Limitations of the Study

- The study is restricted to a limited number of men.
- Study restricted to one geographical area.
- Responses are self-perception.
- Proximity to and position of authority of the researcher may affect responses.
- It does not cover all the possible aspects that the topic can cover including whether a work life balance means the same thing to men as women.
- It is in the nature of an exploratory study and therefore not in-depth.

Further Scope for Study

Attitude toward work life balance are complex. There are many nuances to it that require exploration both from a sociological and socio-psychological point of view. Massive scope exists for expanding the field of study. This study covers only a small section of the society of working men. Huge scope exists in extending this study and covering more men of different geographical, socio-cultural background and ethnicity Exploring the male work-life balance issues of men in different strata of society, different cultural and social background would not only add to literature, it will expand knowledge and give pointers to solutions and remedies which will benefit both men and women alike. A comparative study of perceptions between men and women would throw up interesting results.

Conclusion

In conclusion it can be said that work life balance issues may be issues faced by men also. The study shows that men young and old do recognise the need to share in household chores. Significantly, almost all of them in the survey perform household chores. While women do consider taking children to office at times as a way to tide over a role conflict, no man in the survey has considered that as an option. This is intriguing and is an area for more research. It is essential to recognise the existence of work life balance issues among men also and undertake more research in the field.

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